

EFFECTIVE METHODS FOR IMPROVING WRITING SKILLS

M. Boyqobilova¹, A. Rustamova²

Abstract:

Writing is one of the powerful modes of communication. It is a complex process that allows writers to explore thoughts and ideas, and make them visible and concrete. teaching with games is very convenient and useful for students to write and remember with interest and desire.

Key words: automation, visual data, collaboration, classroom blog, model-based learning, digital frame, product approach, personal and public writing, revising, editing, proof-reading, word-selecting, visual and kinaesthetic analysis.

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Writing is one of the powerful modes of communication. It is a complex process that allows writers to explore thoughts and ideas, and make them visible and concrete. As E. Olshtain states, writing encourages thinking and learning for it motivates communication and makes thought available for reflection. When thought is written down, ideas can be examined, reconsidered, added to, rearranged, and changed. Successful written communication is extremely important in the modern world as interaction takes the form of not only traditional paper- and-pencil writing but also the most advanced electronic mail.

Features of writing as a skill. According to its role in the process of communication writing is initiative (+speaking), not reactive (as reading and listening). Writing is a productive skill, a developed or acquired ability to produce and reproduce some information in written form. The product of writing is a written text; the result is the ability to produce a written text; the subject of writing is someone's thought expressed in written form.

B1 Threshold Level (the level of school leavers) in writing is categorized by two features. The first feature is the ability to maintain interaction, getting across the information in a range of contexts. The second is the ability to produce a range of texts on familiar matters.

Teaching with games is very convenient and useful for students to write and remember with interest and desire.

- Get away from pen and paper

Writing on something that's not paper, and writing with something that's not a pen or pencil, can help students be really creative. Ask young students to make the shapes of letters with their hands or their bodies. Depending on the number of students you have, they could use stamps, stones, chalk, mini whiteboards or paint. Print out little letters for students to rearrange and use to practise the spelling of new words. It's a great way to get them feeling confident with letters before they write. Check it out below.

¹ *Boyqobilova Madina Umarovna, student of SamSIFL*

² *Rustamova Adash Eshankulovna, teacher of SamSIFL*

Though the nature of writing as a skill used to be underestimated in language teaching, the written aspect of a foreign language has gained more significance nowadays. Traditionally, writing was viewed mainly as a means of teaching grammar or sentence structure, an effective tool for practising language patterns, “a fairly one- dimensional activity” (Ch. Tribble). Nowadays we realize the importance of writing in human interaction, and the first reason why writing is included in a foreign- language syllabus is that people frequently have to communicate with each other in a written form in real-life situations. T. Hedge differentiates six types of every-day writing, important in real life intercourse:

- Personal writing (diaries, journals, shopping lists, recipes, etc.),
- Public writing (letters of enquire/complaint/request, form-filling, etc.),

Tasks for process approach include story writing, cooperative writing, or peer correction of subsequent drafts. Different researches show that writing as a process includes the following activities:

- setting the goal for the written communication;
- assessing the reader;
- gathering information and generating ideas;
- organizing writing a draft;
- revising, editing and proofreading.

Nowadays the distinction between these two approaches seems to be less clear and teaching writing combines both approaches, with slight emphasis on product writing as far as beginner learners are concerned. It is possible, then, to teach writing in classroom using different approaches and a variety of activities. Moreover, the attention should be given both to the linguistic-accuracy level and to the message-transmission level. It is the combination of content and organization with accepted formal features that will lead learners to better utilization of the writing skill in their future use of English.

The role of vocabulary in developing writing. It is experience of most language teachers that the single, biggest component of any language course is vocabulary. If language structures, says Jeremy Harmer, make up the skeleton of language, then it is vocabulary that provides the vital organs and the flesh. For many years vocabulary was seen as incidental to the main purpose of language teaching - the acquisition of grammatical knowledge about the language.

Recently the status of vocabulary has been considerably enhanced. This has come about mainly as a result of the development of communicative approaches, proponents of which point out that the acquisition of an adequate vocabulary is essential for successful FL use otherwise comprehensible communication can hardly be possible. The problem is what words and idioms students should retain, what are the principles and criteria of vocabulary selection. Different scholars (M. West, McCarthy, Richards, and Galina Rogova) name the following: frequency, coverage or range of contents, ease, learnability, familiarity, learners' needs.

Word frequency is an example of purely linguistic approach to word selection. It is claimed to be the soundest criterion because it is completely objective. But frequency does not necessarily equate with usefulness or relevance to learner needs and coverage or range of contents may be more important. The useful words for learner are those which occur across a wide variety of texts. The next criterion for vocabulary selection for teaching purposes is ease with which words may be learned. For example, abstract items are more difficult to learn than words that denote concrete things, actions or qualities.

The ease or difficulty a word presents depends on variety of different reasons, and may need special attention or focus in teaching. According to Michael McCarthy learnability of words is an important criterion which should be taken into account selecting vocabulary for teaching purposes. Words with low learnability cause some problems for students (e.g. spelling or phonological difficulties, vague or half-comprehended cultural setting, words may be perceived as very close in meaning by the learners and then confused, etc.).

Words with high learnability do not cause additional difficulties and may be more familiar to learners. The criterion of familiarity is a concept incorporating frequency, meaningfulness, concreteness (Richards). Learners who are familiar with a particular sphere of life (e.g. physics, economics, etc.) will find the words connected with the sphere less difficult to learn. It is important to understand that different learners need differentiated vocabulary lists, and that the list should reflect the communicative needs of learners. Thus, an important criterion for selection is learners' needs.

Teacher and coursebook writer should predict learners' communicative needs and equip learner with the basic core of language (the most common grammatical and lexical items) and a survival vocabulary, creating at the same time a sense of need for a word in learners. The selection of vocabulary, though important, is not teacher's chief concern. Teacher's concern is how to get their students to assimilate the vocabulary prescribed. Teacher should bear in mind that a word is considered to be learned when:

- it is spontaneously recognized while listening and reading;
- it is correctly used in speech (oral/written), the right word in the right place.

Real vocabulary that learner possesses serves both productive and receptive purposes. When producing speech (while speaking/writing) learner operates freely some words, word-combinations, and expressions for their communicative purposes, their vocabulary is called active/functional/productive vocabulary. When comprehending wide variety of texts and utterances (while listening and reading) learner is able to understand but not yet use the vocabulary, it is called passive / recognition/receptive. Learners can be seriously under-equipped to deal with authentic language if they neglect to extend their passive /receptive vocabulary and develop their potential vocabulary.

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